

THE IMPORTANCE OF THE EDUCATION IN DEMOCRACY BUILDING IN MACEDONIA- CHALLENGES FROM TEACHER'S POINT OF VIEW

Isamet Bakiu

Democracy plus – Macedonia Skopje

E-mail: isamet.bakiu7@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Democracy building is closely related to the people who live in a certain country. Democracy is “the rule of demos” and “demos” is understood as “the people”. Those who have the right to vote they have the power to change the leadership. “Either kings should become philosophers or philosophers become kings,” says Plato in his work *The Republic*. The knowledge obtained in schools does not always prepare people to rule. Sometimes or most of the time it prepares people to serve. In a small country like Macedonia we have a democracy, which implements a power sharing as a form of conflict management after the 2001 conflict. The recognition of the right to education at the university level calmed down interethnic tensions and paved the road to the building of the consociational democracy. Despite of it the education system in Macedonia faces many difficulties and challenges.

Keywords: democracy, education, challenges, accountability, transfers of knowledge and reforms.

Introduction

Preschool, elementary and secondary education levels are the vital for education of younger generations. The challenges that are considered main strategic issues will be briefly explained through reflection on other existing education systems in the world and obstacles that teachers face during their teaching work. Basically due to large numbers of pupil teachers fail to dedicate same time and attention to all pupils equally. Teachers do not receive on job training during the school year. Curricula are overwhelmingly involving too much theory that pupil will not need in their life after school. Relationships teacher-student-parent-teacher is not functioning properly.

1. Focusing on Pupils and Students

The paper puts roughly many challenges or strategic issues faced in the elementary or secondary school level, which are prerequisite to a proper reform in the system. Despite the detailed and promising Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Education and Science for 2017-2020, it seems that a lot needs to be done in order the pupils to feel those changes in their school life every day. But still there is a need for a new start that puts education as the first priority. "If you want to destroy an entire nation, then you firstly destroy its family structure, secondly its education and thirdly lower the role models," says an oriental proverb. The education of the children starts in the womb of their mothers. It is so important that the mother is well educated about how to raise its baby, but that's not the case for all the mothers. All that way from womb to tomb is a long journey and so many challenges that come and go. In a democracy all people are supposed to enjoy all rights equally. Children's rights are of particular importance. Governments are obliged to provide all necessary conditions and legal frameworks to implement and promote Human Rights. John Dewey explains very well the chronological concept of education in democracy since the time of Plato, the individualist of the XVIII century to the idealists of the XIX century.

2. Teaching and on job training

The teacher, on the other hand, has his own responsibility in relation to the students. This responsibility can be compared with the doctor's care about their patients. If the doctor is responsible for the health or the life of a human being, the teacher on the other hand is responsible both for the health and its mental development. In Finland, teachers are highly ranked in a society as well as lawyers, doctors, engineers etc. Their incomes are high enough that they consider the workplace as a place where they can make a life career. This is unfortunately not the case in our country. Apart from its full time school work, the teacher is considering working as a waiter or a taxi driver in order to feed his family. This does not give teachers time to deal with their students or to conduct research on advanced methods or follow international trends in education. Of course the main and crucial problem is the human resources sector. Another issue is the mentality, the attitude of the people toward the rule of law, human rights and democracy in general. People must be taught these values continuously and they must be promoted as universal values that will contribute in changing the status quo.

3. Between Education and Business

Systems of international certification and evaluation can clear the legal competitiveness among scholars and quasi scholars in local level. It may also regulate the competitiveness among private institutions of education and prevent possible

business purposes such as bids and various manipulations for personal interests or political influences and pressures. Why children should not have equal access? Is it better to create equal opportunities by a reformed public education? It should prevent education from becoming a business mainly because it risks even a democracy in one country as it gives more space to quasi scholars question and neglect the real intellectuals in a society. It really harms the Democracy and sets the pyramid of values abruptly. Living in the time of internet is an advantage of course. The existence of many educational sites and virtual schools, online libraries and other apps are really making pupils' life easier. There is need for a patient teacher that can path their way to knowledge. Children do not like just to work all the time or to make multiple choice tests or tasks that create a lot of stress for them. Schools should be places of joy for students. Satisfaction in learning really helps the brain function well better and enlarges the brain weeds. The teacher's main job is to motivate the pupil but they must be motivated too.

Education should stop being business. Permanent workshops and trainings on job, as well as supervised monitoring by students before graduation who attend classes depending on their field of study can contribute to the improvement of teaching and learning process. Schools should be workplaces where the teacher is satisfied and happy, but on the other hand, the students will be happy and motivated. Mutuality, honesty and discipline in the workplace are prerequisites to create trust between parents, students and teachers. The penalties are not solving problems in education, but a process improving system that will bring change in a long run. The main point is to teach children how to use their knowledge. We should not make them learn by heart. Let's learn how to be skillful and how to solve problems. "We only think when we are confronted with problems," says Dewey. All subjects should be taught by using case studies that bring knowledge, joy and fun.

Conclusion

The education has a crucial impact because it prepares the generations that will be able to continue with the development of Democracy in the country. At the same time as the country is aiming to join NATO and the broader work market the EU market, reforms should consider the market demands in the forthcoming union of states. Preschool, elementary and secondary schools are the most important parts in the creation of skillful market driven work force and reforms should cover basically every strategic issue and set strategic plans for reform and development. Vocational education and education in the construction sector should prepare students for the labor market of the country, the region and broader. Setting standards of educating

teachers at the University and building systems human and intellectual capacities to enable them follow contemporary education and teaching trends.

References

1. Dewey, J. (1916/1985). *Democracy and Education*. Indiana; Southern Illinois UP.
2. Ashton, David and Francis Green (1996) *Education, Training and the Global Economy*, (Cheltenham, Edward Elgar).
3. Sisk, Timothy D. *Power Sharing and Mediation in Ethnic Conflic*. New York: Carnegie Corporation of new York, 1996
4. Bieber, Florian. *“Post Conflict Institutions in Ethnically divided Societies. From Power-Sharing to Democracy.”* London:McGill-Queen’s University press, 2005
5. Plato, *The Republic*, by Alan Bloom translation
6. <http://www.inp.uw.edu.pl/mdsie/Political Thought/Plato-Republic.pdf>
7. Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Education and Science of Republic of Macedonia [http://www.mon.gov.mk/images/documents/Strateshki_plan MON/Strateski plan_2018-2020_12.01.20181.pdf](http://www.mon.gov.mk/images/documents/Strateshki_plan_MON/Strateski_plan_2018-2020_12.01.20181.pdf)
8. OECD:<http://www.oecd.org/education/>